

D1.7 –Updated Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication plan

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents the revision of the EPOS ON Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (D1.6), at PM 18. The Plan is dedicated to ensuring effective outreach, engagement, and sustainability of project results. By aligning with EPOS' strategic goals, the plan enhances scientific collaboration, technological advancements, and societal benefits, ensuring EPOS ON's contributions remain impactful beyond the project's duration. The revision covers aspects that have assumed more importance as the project proceeds (e.g. engagement of the multi-risk community), as well as emerging contents (e.g. how to best give visibility to intermediate project results). It also includes a non-exhaustive table of events the project plans to participate in during period 2.

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TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
DoA	Description of Action
ECR	Early Career Researchers
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ICS	Integrated Core Services
KMT	Krafla Magma Testbed
KoM	Kick off Meeting
NRI	National Research Infrastructure
OO	Operational Objective
OS	Open Science
PC	Project Council
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCC	Service Coordination Committee
SG	Strategic Goal
TCS	Thematic Core Services
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	1
2. Introduction	2
3. Objectives and target audiences	4
3.1. Target audiences	4
3.2. Objectives of the Plan	4
3.3. Approach.....	5
3.4. Monitoring, measuring, improving.....	5
4. Communication	6
4.1. Branding and messaging	7
4.1.1. Key concepts and messaging.....	7
4.1.2. Visual Identity.....	7
4.2. Website & Social Media	8
4.3. Printed & Digital Materials	9
4.4. Events: the EPOS Days	10
4.5. Focus: visibility of intermediate results.....	10
5. Dissemination	12
5.1. Publications	12
5.2. Workshops and conferences	13
5.3. Collaboration with other research infrastructures	14
6. Exploitation	15
6.1. Open Science (OS) & FAIR: promoting output reusability	15
6.2. Integration of new project outputs in the EPOS service portfolio	17
6.3. Training and capacity building	17
6.4. Engagement of non-academic audiences	18
6.4.1. Engagement with the multi-risk community.....	18
7. Conclusions	20
8. References	21
9. Appendix I – EPOS ON logo and visual identity	22

9.1.	Main logo	22
9.1.1.	Monochrome versions:	22
9.2.	Colour palette.....	23
9.3.	PPT template	23
9.4.	MS Word templates.....	25
9.5.	EPOS ON events' visual identity and templates.....	27
9.6.	Canva branding kit and templates	29
10.	<i>Appendix II – GA requirements for communication and dissemination activities and materials</i>	<i>30</i>
10.1.	Acknowledgement of EU funding and European flag visibility	30
10.2.	Data Protection Rules	31
11.	<i>Appendix III - Events organized by EPOS ON (Project period 1).....</i>	<i>33</i>
12.	<i>Appendix IV - Events organized by EPOS ON (Project period 2).....</i>	<i>35</i>
13.	<i>Appendix V – Participation to external events – Project period 2</i>	<i>37</i>

1. Executive Summary

The EPOS ON project plays a pivotal role in strengthening and evolving the EPOS Research Infrastructure (RI). This document outlines a comprehensive strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation to ensure the effective promotion, uptake, and sustainability of EPOS ON's results.

The strategy aligns with the EPOS Operational Communication Plan 2024-2028¹ and is structured around three key aspects:

1. **Communication** – Raising awareness and ensuring visibility of EPOS ON's activities, goals, and achievements through targeted branding, media engagement, and digital platforms.
2. **Dissemination** – Sharing research outputs with relevant stakeholders, including the scientific community, industry, policymakers, and the public, to maximize the impact and usability of project findings.
3. **Exploitation** – Ensuring that project results lead to tangible benefits through integration into EPOS services, policy recommendations, and engagement with industry and research infrastructures.

By integrating these three aspects into a cohesive plan, EPOS ON will maximise its outreach and ensure its contributions to the scientific community and society at large remain impactful and enduring.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14860590>

2. Introduction

EPOS ON is EPOS' flagship project, aiming to support the consolidation of the infrastructure while paving the way for its future evolution. Hence, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation objectives of EPOS ON are intertwined to the overall EPOS strategy, and in particular the EPOS Operational Communication Plan 2024-2028².

This updated strategy aligns the EPOS ON dissemination and communication objectives with the overarching strategic goals (SG) outlined in the EPOS Operational Communication Plan for 2024-2028:

- **SG0 - Visibility:** Enhance global awareness of EPOS ON activities and outcomes through robust branding and digital outreach.
- **SG1 - Positioning:** Establish EPOS as a global leader in solid Earth science infrastructure, emphasizing its innovative contributions.
- **SG2 - Internal Communication:** Strengthen collaboration between EPOS ON, TCS, NRIs, and other stakeholders to ensure unified messaging.
- **SG3 - Foster Usage:** Promote the utilization and re-use of EPOS services and data to broaden their impact.
- **SG4 - Community Engagement:** Expand outreach to diverse stakeholder groups, including researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and society.

The table shows the operational objectives listed in the communication plan and connects them to the strategic goals. All communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives in the present plan also need to align to these operational objectives.

Objectives that are directly impacted by the EPOS ON communication, dissemination and exploitation plan are highlighted in yellow.

Objective	Short Description	Related Goal(s)
OO1- Branding	Reinforce EPOS branding and implement it consistently across TCS and NRIs	SG0 - SG1 - SG2
OO2 - Website review	Evolve the EPOS website and increase its visibility	SG0 - SG1 - SG2 - SG4

² <https://zenodo.org/records/14860590>

Objective	Short Description	Related Goal(s)
OO3 - Information materials	Provide a variety of informative materials on EPOS and its activities	SG0 - SG1 - SG4
OO4 - EPOS videos	Provide informative and engaging videos about EPOS, its activities and its users	SG0 - SG1 - SG4
OO5 - Social media	Consolidate the EPOS presence on social media and grow its audience	SG0 - SG1 - SG4
OO6 - Event planning	Create moments for the EPOS community to meet together and engage with stakeholders	SG0 - SG1 - SG2 - SG3 - SG4
OO7 - Training and user engagement	Train and engage users to make the most of the EPOS Data Portal (EPOS Platform)	SG1 - SG2 - SG3 - SG4
OO8 - Community & employer branding	Encourage young talents to join EPOS	SG1 - SG4
OO9 - EPOS Open Source positioning	Position and disseminate the EPOS Data Portal (EPOS Platform) Open Source code	SG1 - SG3 - SG4
OO10 - Internal and external communication tools	Enhance the communication flow with different target audiences	SG2 - SG4

3. Objectives and target audiences

3.1. Target audiences

EPOS ON engages a broad spectrum of stakeholders to ensure effective dissemination and impact:

- **Scientific Community:** Researchers, data providers, and users in solid Earth and multidisciplinary sciences, including early career researchers.
- **IT Community:** Engineers, data scientists, and technical practitioners supporting research infrastructure development.
- **Research Infrastructures:** Professionals across scientific, legal, technical, and managerial roles.
- **Policy-Makers:** National governments, the European Commission, ESFRI, and funding agencies.
- **Private Sector:** Industry partners, including small and medium enterprises, leveraging EPOS data and services.
- **General Public:** Students, educators, media, and broader society, fostering awareness and engagement with EPOS initiatives.

Engaging with these groups is a key objective of the project and a critical factor for the long-term uptake and sustainability of its results. Engagement is not limited to the dissemination and communication tasks or the work package dedicated to engagement; rather, it is a cross-cutting action throughout the project. In this perspective, the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan serves as a strategic tool to coordinate these actions coherently and provide project participants with clear guidelines.

3.2. Objectives of the Plan

The plan's objectives fall into two categories:

1. Project-Specific Objectives
 - Raise awareness of project activities within and beyond the project community.
 - Encourage participation from target groups to maximize impact through co-creation and community validation.
 - Facilitate the dissemination, communication, and exploitation of project outputs.
2. Overall Communication and Dissemination of EPOS Results
 - Aligned with the EPOS Communication Plan referenced in the introduction.

3.3. Approach

EPOS ON follows a structured strategy to maximize impact through three key pillars: **communication, dissemination, and exploitation** while ensuring that EPOS ON remains aligned with the overarching EPOS goals, leveraging enhanced tools and frameworks to maximize communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts.

- **Communication** aims to raise awareness of EPOS ON among scientists, policymakers, industry, and the public, ensuring visibility, engagement, and knowledge-sharing through diverse channels.
- **Dissemination** ensures research results reach relevant stakeholders—scientists, policymakers, and industry professionals—who can apply them effectively.
- **Exploitation** focuses on transforming research outcomes into innovation, service adoption, and policy contributions for long-term societal benefits.

3.4. Monitoring, measuring, improving

EPOS ERIC's Communication Unit periodically collects information from all the actors involved in EPOS, in particular TCS and National Nodes and consortia, in order to 1) timely discover exposure opportunities and plan and prioritise the support to EPOS' presence in national, regional and disciplinary communication and dissemination activities, including events, publications and presentations to different audiences, as well as the creation and localisation of printed and multimedia materials 2) collect KPIs relevant to communication and dissemination, measure the results and 3) evaluate the effectiveness of the interventions, and discuss possible improvements and share best practices and success stories with the involved partners. To this end, a network of communication contacts is in place within EPOS, which is animated by the Communication Unit and meets periodically in person or virtually. This existing mechanism will be exploited in the framework of EPOS ON, and complemented with the information provided by WP leaders during OEB meetings and in periodic reports in order to keep track of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities that are specifically relevant to EPOS ON.

4. Communication

The EPOS ON communication activities are focused on raising awareness about the project's challenges and goals, activities and achievements, both within the project community and among a broad audience including scientists, policymakers, industry, and the general public. The goal is to ensure visibility, engagement, and knowledge-sharing using various channels and tools. In a broader perspective, this also applies to the EPOS Research Infrastructure in general.

The communication strategy has two key components:

1. Internal Communication

- Build a close-knitted project community and emphasize two-way communication through dedicated communication tools and regular meetings, both online and in-person.
- Organize the **EPOS Days**, an annual event that unites the EPOS community, highlights key project milestones, and advances EPOS ON activities.

2. External Communication

- Invite to the EPOS Days external partners, new potential scientific communities and other relevant stakeholders outside the project Community and organise public sessions to maximise the awareness about EPOS ON (and more generally the EPOS RI).
- Develop dedicated project pages within the EPOS website.
- Enhance EPOS' social media presence with tailored content showcasing the project's objectives and activities.
- Produce communication materials (leaflets, presentations, posters, and branded merchandise) for events and meetings.

Key Activities for this area include:

- **Branding & Messaging:** Establish a clear identity through consistent branding and messaging across all platforms.
- **Website & Social Media:** Maintain an updated website and actively engage³ on LinkedIn and YouTube. BlueSky is also being considered for the near future.
- **Printed & Digital Materials:** Produce brochures, infographics, and newsletters for diverse audiences.
- **Events:** Organisation of online and face-to-face project events

The main communication tools foreseen are the following:

³ Presence on social media "X" (formerly "Twitter") was discontinued as of December 2024.

- Project mailing lists and groups
- EPOS website and social media channels
- Visual identity kit with templates for official documents
- Communication toolbox (ready-to-use and customisable flyers, banners, videos, digital assets).

4.1. Branding and messaging

4.1.1. Key concepts and messaging

The name *EPOS ON* (EPOS Optimisation and evolution) reflects its core mission: strengthening the EPOS research infrastructure while paving the way for its future evolution. The project is dedicated to ensuring EPOS RI's long-term sustainability by demonstrating its value to the scientific and IT communities, and by generating new insights to address major societal challenges.

A key aspect of EPOS ON's strategy is leveraging and expanding the EPOS community, recognizing its role as a foundation for innovation and sustainability. The project is built around three core principles:

- **Innovation:** Ensuring EPOS remains at the forefront of scientific and technological advancements.
- **Evolution:** Supporting the continuous improvement and adaptation of EPOS to meet emerging needs.
- **Participation:** Strengthening integration across data, communities, and stakeholders to foster engagement and collaboration.

These principles guide both the technical progress of EPOS ON and its communication efforts, ensuring broad engagement with its objectives and long-term impact.

4.1.2. Visual Identity

The EPOS ON visual identity was designed to maintain continuity with the core EPOS brand while establishing a distinct and recognizable look. The logo adapts the EPOS branding by incorporating the word *ON* in a graphical design that resembles a power button, symbolizing activation and progress. This reinforces the project's role as a catalyst for the strategic evolution of EPOS infrastructure.

To support consistent branding across all communications, the visual identity kit includes⁴:

- **Logo and graphical elements** to ensure unified representation.

⁴ See Appendix 1

- **Templates** for documents, deliverables, presentations, and outreach materials.
- **Templates for printed and digital assets** such as leaflets, postcards, and promotional materials.

The visual identity kit was introduced at the project Kick-off Meeting (KoM) and provided to all partners with recommendations on template usage. This ensures coherent communication and reinforces the EPOS ON message across all platforms and engagements.

4.2. Website & Social Media

In line with the EPOS ON branding and messaging discussed above, we position EPOS ON web and social media presence as a part of the general one for EPOS, opting not to create separate social media profiles or a standalone website. This decision is both **practical and strategic**:

- **Maximizing Visibility & Engagement** – Building an audience for new social media accounts and achieving strong website indexing takes time. Leveraging EPOS' existing platforms ensures immediate visibility and reach.
- **Focusing on Content Creation** – Instead of investing effort in growing a separate follower base, resources can be directed toward producing engaging content.
- **Ensuring Long-Term Impact** – By integrating EPOS ON within EPOS' channels, the community built during the project remains engaged beyond its duration.

To differentiate EPOS ON within the broader EPOS presence, the following strategies are implemented:

- **Consistent EPOS ON branding** to maintain a distinct visual identity.
- **Use of the #EPOSon hashtag** for all project-related social media content.
- **A dedicated EPOS ON section** on the EPOS website, continuously updated as the project progresses.

This approach enhances visibility, strengthens engagement, and ensures sustainability beyond the project's lifetime.

4.3. Printed & Digital Materials

The project communication team develops both **ready-to-use** and **customizable** materials, including flyers, brochures, infographics, posters, banners, slide sets, videos, and other digital assets⁵.

- **Ready-to-use materials** are available in PDF and other widely used formats, with print-ready versions including clear instructions for printing services. This approach is particularly beneficial for non-professional communicators and accommodates EPOS' widespread consortium, making centralized printing and distribution impractical. It also enhances **cost-effectiveness, sustainability, and relevance**, as partners print only what they need, when they need it, ensuring materials remain up to date.
- **Customizable materials** are provided in editable formats with appropriate licenses to **maximize reuse** within and beyond the project community. In addition to standard assets like leaflets and presentations, a **Canva branding kit and templates** enable partners to

⁵ See also Appendix 1

create tailored materials independently. This flexibility is crucial for **quick-turnaround needs** and the **efficient production of localized materials** in EPOS' various languages.

This strategy ensures accessibility, adaptability, and sustainability in EPOS ON's communication efforts.

4.4. Events: the EPOS Days

Events (and especially face-to-face periodical meetings) are a key to build and reinforce the project community (as well as the EPOS community at large). A pivotal element is in particular the organisation of the EPOS Days, a yearly meeting designed to act as the main meeting point for the different stakeholders in and around the EPOS' community and to:

- discuss project progress and exploitation with WP leaders (i.e., Optimization and Evolution Board meetings);
- interact with the EPOS ON beneficiaries on project progress and results (i.e., PC meeting);
- disseminate the EPOS ON progress and results amongst the wide EPOS scientific community;
- reinforce cooperation with representatives of pan-European and international initiatives;
- create awareness amongst societal stakeholders, such as operational disaster risk managers;
- invite representatives from specific target groups, such as early career researchers and infrastructure managers.

4.5. Focus: visibility of intermediate results

With the project now having reached its mid-term, communication and dissemination activities will be further strengthened through a targeted effort to increase the visibility of the intermediate results achieved so far in line with the project schedule. This complementary stream of activities builds upon the existing plan and leverages, whenever possible, already available materials (e.g. presentations, reports and technical outputs), ensuring a sustainable approach that does not place significant additional burden on the coordinator or partners.

These communication activities address multiple target groups:

- First and foremost, the project participants and the EPOS community at large, including Thematic Core Services, Integrated Core Services, governance bodies and the wider scientific communities, will be engaged to ensure awareness, alignment and feedback, and a quicker uptake of new services and other actionable results.
- Partners, funders and relevant organisations will be targeted in order to reinforce the positioning of EPOS and highlight the added value generated through the project.

- The broader geoscientific community will be addressed, with particular attention to early career researchers, who represent a key audience in terms of uptake potential and future adoption/furthering of the results.

These activities will be implemented through a coordinated set of actions, including:

- the adaptation of the EPOS Days programme to explicitly showcase intermediate results and create dedicated spaces for community feedback and co-creation of further developments;
- strengthened internal communication, such as regular updates from the coordinator to partners and targeted highlights to governance bodies (e.g. Project Council);
- publication of articles and dedicated web pages on institutional platforms;
- dissemination through social media channels and targeted outreach via partners' communication tools (e.g. newsletters and community mailing lists).

Overall, this approach is envisaged to ensure a coherent, resource-efficient amplification of results, maximising their visibility and impact at a crucial stage of the project lifecycle.

5. Dissemination

The EPOS ON dissemination activities ensure that the project's research results reach relevant stakeholders who can utilize them effectively. It targets in the first place the scientific community, but also other target groups such as policymakers, civil protection agencies and industry players who can integrate findings into their work.

Key activities for this action area include:

- **Scientific Publications, Policy Briefs and Reports:** Share the findings and results through channels tailored to specific target groups
- **Workshops & Conferences:** Present research at major scientific events such as EGU, AGU, IUGG and other international events.
- **Collaboration with Other Research Infrastructures:** Foster partnerships to amplify impact and organise thematic workshops to facilitate the exchange with them.

Training & Capacity Building activities are also pivotal to enhance dissemination, but they are discussed in the next chapter since they also have a major impact on the exploitation of the project's results.

The main tools and channels to carry out the dissemination activities include:

- Open-access repositories and journals
- Conferences, symposia, and technical meetings
- Training materials and e-learning platforms
- EPOS Days and targeted stakeholder events

5.1. Publications

Publications are a key channel for sharing EPOS ON's scientific and technical findings with different audiences. The communication team **encourages, coordinates, and supports** the production of various publication types, including:

- Peer-reviewed journal articles for researchers
- **Policy briefs** for policymakers and decision-makers
- Technical reports and documentation for IT experts
- White papers/position statements for other RIs and partners

To **maximize the FAIRness and visibility** of project publications and those citing EPOS ON, guidelines on licensing and proper citation are provided. A **Zenodo community** is available for project participants to share deliverables, outputs, and relevant external publications. This repository is part of the EU-funded Open Research collection⁶, and is available at the following URL: https://zenodo.org/communities/epos_on/

Additionally, EPOS ON ensures proper citation of the EPOS platform and relevant datasets and scientific products through the application of the **EPOS Data, Data Products, Software, and Services (DDSS) Citation Guide**⁷.

5.2. Workshops and conferences

The project communication team keeps a shared calendar of international, national and thematic events that provide a good opportunity to showcase EPOS ON, its activities and results and engage with relevant audiences. Presence at major international events is managed centrally, while representation at national/regional/local and thematic events is the responsibility of relevant partners, with the project communication team in a support role (to provide content and materials, help advertising EPOS ON presence and track, analyse and report the results).

Participation in these events can take multiple forms depending on the specific objectives, opportunities and resources available, aspects that are discussed case by case, involving specific partners when appropriate. They include:

- Invited presentations
- Submission of abstracts for poster or oral presentations
- Short courses and seminars
- Dissemination of communication materials
- Booth presence

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/>

⁷ <https://10.5281/zenodo.15022118>

5.3. Collaboration with other research infrastructures

Several actions are envisaged to strengthen the sharing of scientific and technical information with sister research infrastructures (e.g. AuScope⁸, EarthScope⁹, Earth Sciences NZ¹⁰) in the context of EPOS ON. These include:

- The establishment of two-way communication channels and tools to share relevant documentation (e.g. slack, mailing lists, shared folders...)
- Organisation of periodical meetings (face-to-face and online)
- Joint organisation of events addressing common topics (e.g. data interoperability)
- joint participation in major events (International Data Week, EGU annual conference, ICRI...), with the objective of presenting common perspectives (e.g. Research Infrastructure federation, role of global collaboration among infrastructures to address key challenges such as sustainability and data preservation)
- collaboration on training and capacity building (e.g. by involving speakers and participants from AuScope, EarthScope and Earth Sciences NZ in the EPOS Summer School).

A scouting activity to identify and map cross-continent collaborations at the level of the scientific communities served by the different RIs was planned and jointly designed in the form of an online survey addressing large consortia and collaborations, to be widely disseminated in the RIs' networks. The main goal of the survey is to identify potential scientific use cases to prioritize and use in communication as success stories cross-continental collaboration in solid Earth sciences. After a promising round of data collection that allowed to identify a first set of priorities (presented in the occasion of the EPOS Days 2026), it was decided to keep the survey as an ongoing activity so as to map new initiatives, as well the capacity of reaching out to new groups, and identify new global scientific use cases.

Initiatives such as personnel exchanges/visits can also be considered on a case-by-case basis if additional funding is available.

⁸ <https://www.auscope.org.au/>

⁹ <https://www.earthscope.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.gns.cri.nz/> Note to the updated edition: Earth Sciences NZ, formerly GNS-Science NZ, has formally joined the multilateral collaboration in 2025 with the kick-off of the new legal entity, but the previous version mentioned GNS.

6. Exploitation

Exploitation activities focus on ensuring the uptake of EPOS ON results in the scientific community, as well as fostering the knowledge transfer to other stakeholders, contributing to innovation and policy development, and through this to long-term societal benefits.

Key Activities in this area include:

- **Open Science & FAIR Principles:** Promote the project outputs' reusability through adherence to open science policies.
- **Integration of new services and outputs into the EPOS Service portfolio:** Ensure that research outputs contribute to improving EPOS RI's operational framework.
- **Training & Capacity Building activities:** organise summer schools and training events and create training materials to lower adoption barriers and engage a wider user base, with special attention to Early Career Researchers.
- **Engagement with non-academic audiences:** foster the transfer of project results to non-academic audiences, in particular industry players and policymakers.

Key exploitation tools include:

- Data management and access frameworks
- Engagement with industry and policy forums
- Policy briefs and recommendations

6.1. Open Science (OS) & FAIR: promoting output reusability

The project communication team provides information about how to produce FAIR-by-design project outputs and adopting appropriate licensing schemes depending on the specific scientific output, in compliance with the EPOS Data policy. A licensing cheatsheet (see table below) was shared with all WP leaders for dissemination within their work packages and guidance is offered on a case-by-case basis.

Scientific output	Licensing scheme	Examples
Metadata	Public Domain Public Domain plus credits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Commons 0 (CC0) • Public Domain Mark • Public Domain Dedication • Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and license (PDDL)

Scientific output	Licensing scheme	Examples
	Attribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) • ODC Attribution • ISA Open Metadata licence
Data (not organised)	Public Domain Public Domain plus credits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Commons 0 (CC0) • Public Domain Mark • Public Domain Dedication • Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and license (PDDL)
Datasets and databases	Attribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) • Open Data Commons Attribution licence
Content	Attribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) • Digital Peer Publishing Licences (DPPL) • GNU Free Documentation Licence (GFDL)¹¹
Software	Open Source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MIT license, • Apache License 2.0, • Mozilla Public License 2.0, • GNU General Public License (GPL) • Common Development and Distribution License • EUPL - F/OSS¹²
Third-party and derivative works	Depending on original license	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on the original license; the general rule is that the license is the same license or more restrictive than the original. <p>Data providers are responsible to check for license compatibility before sharing third party outputs or derivatives through EPOS</p>

¹¹ DPPL and GFDL only apply to textual works

¹² The full list of available OS licenses can be found on the Open Source Initiative website <https://opensource.org/osd>

6.2. Integration of new project outputs in the EPOS service portfolio

In collaboration with WP2 and WP3 a process will be implemented to make sure that the new services and features developed in the framework of WP2 and WP3 are integrated in the EPOS service portfolio and made available to users as soon as they reach the right level of maturity. This process will rely on existing structures within EPOS, in particular the ICS-TCS coordination.

This will also apply to other project outputs, such as the new releases of EPOS' Open Source code and any other relevant software.

Extra care will be posed into incorporating the user feedback collected throughout the project through:

- Collection of spontaneous feedback (i.e. from the portal)
- Collection of structured feedback in occasion of training events and hands-on session
- User surveys, questionnaires and interviews
- Dedicated focus groups (EPOS User Feedback group)

This will allow implementing a continuous improvement cycle.

6.3. Training and capacity building

EPOS ON fosters user engagement with the EPOS Platform through tailored learning paths, a network of trainers, and reusable training resources. The activity is mainly carried out in the framework of WP4 but is supported through a horizontal action of the project.

This activity will drive the collection of training needs via surveys and interviews to shape an engagement strategy and proceed to:

- Co-designing learning paths for diverse audiences (e.g., researchers, policymakers, industry, citizen scientists) with the TCSs' involvement.
- Build a network of educators across EPOS countries.
- Develop **FAIR-by-design training materials** with metadata for easy reuse.
- Create a **training hub** to support trainers and trainees and facilitate the communication within the learners' community.

As described in the project's DoA, the organisation of yearly summer schools will be a pivotal moment of this activity, and will also be instrumental to the collection of new use cases for the EPOS platform, to be disseminated in publications and at events.

EPOS Summer Schools are designed to foster learning, collaboration, and long-term engagement within the EPOS community. A programme committee is appointed to develop a structured syllabus and coordinate with expert trainers to shape the learning experience.

The event's concept, learning objectives, and selection criteria for students, were defined during the first project months, and the feedback from the first edition is used to improve the following ones.

6.4. Engagement of non-academic audiences

Dedicated actions are envisaged to engage with non-academic audiences and facilitate knowledge transfer of project results. These include in particular:

- Engaging with industry fora and work with private partners to explore applications of EPOS ON technologies and potential collaborations relevant for them, in particular with reference to the collaboration with the Krafla Magma Testbed (KMT) and WP2 activities, and to the reuse of EPOS Open Source software.
- Engaging with civil servants, public agencies and policy makers, discuss possible collaborations on how EPOS ON findings can inform the decision-making process (in connection with WP3 activities).

6.4.1. Engagement with the multi-risk community

In this context, a specific line of action will focus on the engagement of the multi-risk community, interpreted in a broad and inclusive sense encompassing both the scientific communities working on multi-hazard and multi-risk approaches (e.g. integration of tsunami, earthquake and satellite data and models for prediction, prevention and mitigation) and the wider ecosystem of stakeholders involved in risk management and decision-making processes. These include policy-makers, civil protection authorities, local administrations and, where relevant, citizens and societal actors.

The primary objective of this activity is to promote and contextualise the societal impact services developed within the project. This includes presenting their potential contribution to evidence-based decision making, clarifying the underlying scientific methodologies, and outlining both the role of scientists and the realistic expectations associated with the use of such tools. Particular attention will be given to the introduction and communication of the “ethical labels” foreseen as an output of WP3, as a means to support transparency, trust and responsible use of the services.

Engagement will be pursued at both European and international levels, also leveraging existing and emerging collaborations, including initiatives such as ADMiR¹³ and interactions with the UNDRR¹⁴ framework in Africa. The main channels will consist of direct interaction with targeted stakeholders and participation in relevant events (e.g. CERIS Disaster Research Days), complemented where appropriate by presentations, demonstrations and interactive sessions. This approach aims to foster

¹³ ADMiR = African Disaster Mitigation Research Center, headquartered in Cairo, Egypt

¹⁴ UNDRR = UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction

dialogue between science and society, while promoting the uptake and informed use of project results in real-world decision-making contexts.

7. Conclusions

The EPOS ON Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan ensures that the project's results are effectively shared, utilized, and integrated into long-term strategies. By aligning with EPOS' broader communication goals, this plan enhances visibility, fosters collaboration, and supports the sustainability of research outputs.

Key takeaways include:

- A clear, structured approach to maximize engagement and impact.
- Targeted outreach to scientific, industrial, policy, and public audiences.
- Integration of research findings into practical applications and policy recommendations.
- A commitment to open science principles, ensuring accessibility and reusability of outputs.

Through this approach, the present plan will help strengthen the research infrastructure and ensure that its contributions continue to benefit the scientific community and society in the long term.

This plan will be revised and updated throughout the project lifetime, also building on the analysis of the first results and the feedback collected from the different target audiences, with the objective to streamline the activities and enhance their effectiveness.

8. References

Reference n°	Reference
[R1] EPOS Operational Communication Plan 2024-2028	https://zenodo.org/records/14860590

9. Appendix I – EPOS ON logo and visual identity

9.1. Main logo

The EPOS ON logo consists of the EPOS logo with the addition of the word “ON” in graphics that recall an on/off button. The standard version is in two colours (GREEN Pantone Solid Coated 553 C, YELLOW Pantone Solid Coated 124 C) to be used on a white background:

9.1.1. Monochrome versions:

A black-only version to be applied against light or intermediate backgrounds, when standard version is not suitable for visualization/printing):

A negative version for use on dark backgrounds:

9.2. Colour palette

The main palette is the same of EPOS' and includes the two colours used in the standard logo:

EPOS LOGO COLOURS	C %	M %	Y %	K %	R	G	B	H°	S %	B %	#	PANTONE SOLID COATED
YELLOW	0	37	94	10	229	145	14	36	94	90	d49f2a	124 C
GREEN	80	33	85	60	21	44	21	120	52	17	152c15	553 C

A secondary palette is used in other graphical elements that contribute to the definition of the overall EPOS ON visual identity, such as the decorative line used in templates, titles, and other elements:

EPOS ON PALETTE OF YELLOW	C %	M %	Y %	K %	R	G	B	H°	S %	B %	#	PANTONE SOLID COATED
EPOS GOLDEN	0	37	94	10	229	145	14	36	94	90	d49f2a	124 C
MEDIUM	0	25	87	0	255	198	41	43	83	100	ffc629	123 C
LIGHT	5	12	43	0	246	223	164	42	33	96	f6dfa4	7401 C

9.3. PPT template

Templates use the EPOS ON logo and visual elements and are complete with the indication of the default license and relevant funding grant information, as prescribed in the GA.

They come with presets and instructions to create well-formed slidesets, complying with the project visual identities and the relevant best practices for a clear, readable and usable presentation:

Guidelines for using the template /1

- Text boxes in this template are set to «do not autofit»:
 - this is done on **purpose** and it means that you are supposed to use the default options for titles, subtitles and contents.
 - we have set the defaults for **optimal readability**. If your content is not fitting in the slide, it means that you need two slides or your audience will struggle with reading!
 - Please **do not change the settings** of the template just to add more text in a slide!
- Please **never make any changes to the slide master or the template in general on your own!**
 - If you feel there's something wrong with the template just let us know!

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Guidelines for using the template /2

- As usual with PPT templates, this one includes several layouts: make sure you use the appropriate one:
 - Title slide:** only at the beginning of your presentation
 - Section header:** when you want to divide different parts of the presentation
 - Content slides:** you have different ones depending on the kind of content you need to use.
 - Do not forget to use the **layout without the footer** (with or without title) in case you need to put in the slide big pictures, maps, videos etc that would (partly) overlap with it
 - Prefer the **provided table slide** as format is already set. If you add the table in a second moment, please check that the font is Calibri

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Guidelines for using the template /3

- You should always use the official template font, which is **Calibri** (regular for the text and **bold** for titles).
 - If functional to what you are communicating, **you may use other colours in the content box** (provided they offer enough contrast to be readable in different luminosity conditions) but please try to use the template colours for titles (**forest green** for sections and **black** for cover and slide titles)
 - There might be exceptions to this rules, e.g. if you need to highlight something in the title (see the /3 indicator in this slide's title)
 - The **Author(s) | Contacts | Date – Occasion** box in the slide title is the only instance of a **golden (sub)title**

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Guidelines for using the template /4

- Templates **work best when you create your slide from scratch!**
 - If you need to **copy into the template one or more slides that come from another presentation** with a different template/theme, please:
 - Copy-and-paste the slide(s) in the slide sorter
 - Click on the near the slide (if you have more than one you'll need to repeat the action) and select the «**Destination Theme**»
 - Check if the theme was applied correctly or needs some tweaks
 - You can adjust any part of the transferred slide manually but you may want to try the «Reset» command on the new slide pane:

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9.4.MS Word templates

We created two .docx templates, one for reports, deliverables etc, and the other for basic leaflets, event agendas etc. While more complex designs are foreseen to be managed by the Communication team, these templates can be used by anyone in the project, thus ensuring easy compliance with the project visual identity and funding acknowledgement indications.

DX.Y - Title

Lead Partner: []
 Version: []
 Author(s) (Name, Organization): []
 Status: []
 Dissemination Level: []

Deliverable Abstract

>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

Set of specialized code scripts that allow users to visualize associated data from the EPOS database. Includes a user interface and a set of scripts that can be used to generate reports and visualizations.

Page Break

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QUALITY CONTROL

Date	Name	Organization
Reviewer 1:		
Reviewer 2:		

TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
ECO	Executive Coordinator Office
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
NACB	National Authorities Consultation Board
CEB	Optimization and Evolution Board
WP	Work Package
PC	Project Council
SCC	Service Coordination Committee

Page Break

2. Chapter 2

A bulleted list

- Rem
- Sub-item
- Sub-sub item
- More sub items

Table 1 - Example table

| Column title |
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Table 2 - Another example table

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EPOS ON Project Summary

Project Start: 1st September 2024
 Project Duration: 36 Months
 EC Grant n°: 101131592
 Coordinator: EPOS ERIC
 Project consortium: include 34 partners from 18 countries, including private companies.

Key Goals

- Enhances the EPOS service portfolio.
- Expands institutional & scientific collaborations.
- Supports new Thematic Core Services & broader data access.
- Engages users, particularly early-career researchers, at European & global levels.
- Develops new processing & workflow services to bridge science & the private sector.

Impact

- Fosters knowledge transfer & technological innovation.
- Reduces fragmentation in the European Research Area.
- Strengthens EPOS's ability to unite scientific communities & countries.

Strategic Objectives

- Ensure full exploitation of project results through a Consortium representative of the EPOS community.
- Cultivate multidisciplinary research as the next step needed to boost EPOS impact.
- Enhance & disseminate the EPOS societal value to increase its capacity to trigger socio-economic impact.
- Elaborate a User Strategy able to capture user needs & to evaluate their implementation.
- Reinforce the presence of EPOS in the European & global contexts, through cooperation & networking with relevant organizations & initiatives.
- Strengthen the EPOS long-term sustainability by focusing on actual needs to steer EPOS optimization & evolution.

EPOS ON - Concept Design

The Work Package structure consists of two transversal Work Packages (WP1, WP6) & four vertical Work Packages (WP2-WP5), all of which contribute to WP6.

Work Package Summaries

WP1: Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
 Manages project operations (contractual, financial, strategic), governance, and risk management. Focuses on result dissemination and exploitation while aligning with WP6 to maximize EPOS ERIC's use of outcomes.

WP2: Enhancing Services for Science
 Expands EPOS services, integrating new countries, communities, and private sector data. Develops TCS, IT functionalities, and IC5-D prototypes to support scientific advancement.

WP3: Tackling Societal Challenges
 Supports hazard risk management, develops ethical guidelines with service labels, and explores ways to reduce environmental impact.

WP4: Strengthening User Engagement
 Refines the User Strategy, enhances communication, and implements training for early-career researchers. Promotes multidisciplinary use and builds the EPOS community.

WP5: Expanding Collaborations
 Strengthens global partnerships (Africa, Latin America, US, Japan) and connects with the European Open Science Cloud, broadening EPOS's reach.

WP6: Optimizing and Evolving EPOS RI
 Synthesizes WP outputs for EPOS optimization, updates the Sustainability Plan, and engages new countries. Develops an IT tool for integrated EPOS service management.

Project Partners

EPOS ERIC (project coordinator) |

University of Utrecht |

CNRS |

Royal Observatory of Belgium |

University of Bergen |

Institute of Geophysics - Polish Academy of Science |

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki |

Lulea University of Technology |

Norwegian Geotechnical Institute |

AGH University of Krakow |

GFZ - Helmholtz Centre Potsdam |

Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences & Arts-ZRC SAZU |

ISPRA |

National Institute for Research & Development for Earth Physics |

EUCENTRE |

Federal Institute for Geology, Geophysics, Climatology & Meteorology |

National Research Council |

University of Oulu |

Geothermal Research Cluster (GEORG) |

Ruder Bošković Institute |

Global Earthquake Model foundation |

Association of the Instituto Superior Técnico for Research & Development |

Icelandic Meteorological Office |

"Federico II" University of Naples |

University Beira Interior |

Božajci University |

National Observatory of Athens |

French Geological Survey - BRGM |

INGV |

Université Grenoble Alpes |

Université Clermont Auvergne |

Landsvirkjun |

Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) |

ETH Zurich |

9.5.EPOS ON events’ visual identity and templates

While events such as the EPOS Days and the EPOS Summer School are organized in the context of EPOS ON and use the branding and EC funding acknowledgement as prescribed, they also are separate events and as such they have their own visual identity which is coordinated (logo, main visual elements, fonts, not necessarily colours which are used to differentiate among different editions) with the EPOS ON main one. The idea here is on one hand give proper visibility to the project and its outcomes, and on the other create a visual identity for events that EPOS plans to continue organizing also in the future, after the end of the project lifetime.

EPOS Days 2025 visual identity: website and slide template usage

EPOS Days 2025 visual identity: poster template and example usage

Summer School Visual identity: Summer School #1 and #2 are differentiated through color palettes

9.6. Canva branding kit and templates

For more advanced users, a brand kit and a set of templates were created on the EPOS ERIC canva workspace, which can be reused by project partners to create their own materials, in compliance with the project visual identity.

10. Appendix II – GA requirements for communication and dissemination activities and materials

10.1. Acknowledgement of EU funding and European flag visibility

In line with the provisions of art. 17 of the Grant Agreement (Communication, Dissemination and Visibility), all communication and dissemination activities and materials created by the beneficiaries must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) in one of its accepted versions¹⁵ (horizontal or vertical, blue with yellow stars, blue, black, white for dark backgrounds etc):

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹⁵ The complete set of EU official logos released for the purpose of acknowledging the EU support in English and the other languages of the EU, are available at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en Complete operational guidelines can be found here: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf Beneficiaries don't need to ask the approval from the granting authority to use the EU emblem for these purposes, as long as they adhere to these provisions

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

EPOS ON is funded by the EC Horizon Europe programme under G.A. n 101131592

The EU emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text, nor can be replaced by other visual elements or logos. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Additionally, all communication or dissemination activity related to EPOS ON must also indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“EPOS ON is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed in this presentation are however those of the Author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

All the project templates already include these indications and visual identity elements, alongside the indication of the license under which the materials are released, which, by default, is CC BY 4.0. EPOS ON partners must take care of including this information when they create materials that do not use the templates (e.g. publications in journals or websites) and, when publishing in repositories (e.g. Zenodo), add them in the metadata.

The open license is adopted in line with the EPOS’ vision that prioritises the open sharing of scientific and technical information with all stakeholders, but it has also the objective to maximise the visibility of the project, in line with the GA requirements in terms of dissemination, communication and promotion of the action. There may be however motivated exceptions to this and partners are responsible for adopting the right license in these cases, also considering what discussed in the chapter on Open Science (OS) & FAIR: promoting output reusability.

10.2. Data Protection Rules

The beneficiaries are the data controllers and thus, responsible for the collection and use of personal data during the project life cycle and even after. The beneficiaries have the obligation to comply

with the Regulation (EU) No 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (OJL119, 4.5.2016, p. 1). Thus, detailed information on the informed consent procedures in regard to data processing must be kept on file. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets must be kept on file.

11. Appendix III - Events organized by EPOS ON (Project period 1)

The following table provides an overview of events to be organised by EPOS ON during the first project year. The table will be updated periodically with new information, as new events are organised. The table does not list the events in which the project is participating, which will be included in the periodic reports.

Responsible partner(s)	Event	Involved Stakeholders	Objectives	Date
EPOS ERIC	EPOS ON KoM	Project Partners and Linked Third Parties, SCC	Kickstart the project and present its vision and roadmap to all partners. Offer Partners a first opportunity to meet in person and discuss the way forward	2-3 October 2025
EPOS ERIC	EPOS DAYS 2025	Project Partners and Linked Third Parties, SCC, the TCS and ICS, ECR, International Partners, New communities	Present the project and its key activities to the wider EPOS Community; Offer an opportunity to progress the work face to face, meeting with relevant stakeholders (e.g. National Nodes and consortia, TCS...) Engage with new communities, international partners and ECR	17-21 March 2025
EPOS ERIC	Meeting on interoperability among global RIs in solid Earth sciences	International RIs in solid Earth sciences (AuScope, EarthScope and GNS-NZ)	Piggiback the EGU 25 event to discuss face to face a roadmap towards the technical interoperability of EPOS with sister infrastructures in Australia, New Zealand and the US	TBC

Responsible partner(s)	Event	Involved Stakeholders	Objectives	Date
EPOS ERIC, UU, INGV	Ministerial track on global collaboration in solid Earth Sciences	Government officials and civil servants at the global level	Piggyback the GEO Global Forum to raise awareness about the importance of collaboration between RIs and the support that can be provided by governments and institutions	5-6 May 2025, Rome (TBC)
EPOS ERIC, CNRS	EPOS ON Summer School 2025	ECR and PHD students	Offer comprehensive training on RDM in solid Earth sciences, providing hands-on session to make the most of the EPOS Platform and learn how to use automated workflows in research work; engage with young researchers and fidelise them to the RI	23-27 June, Olot, (Spain)

12. Appendix IV - Events organized by EPOS ON (Project period 2)

The following table provides an overview of events to be organised by EPOS ON during the second half of the project. The table will be updated periodically with new information, as new events are organised. The table does not list the events in which the project is participating, which will be included in the periodic reports.

Responsible partner(s)	Event	Involved Stakeholders	Objectives	Date
EPOS ERIC	EPOS Days 2026	Project Partners and Linked Third Parties, SCC, the TCS and ICS, ECR, International Partners, New communities	<p>Present the project and its key activities to the wider EPOS Community;</p> <p>Offer an opportunity to progress the work face to face, meetings with relevant stakeholders (e.g. National Nodes and consortia, TCS...)</p> <p>Engage with new communities, international partners and ECR</p>	16-20 March 2026
GEORG, Landsvjurkin, EPOS ERIC	Superhot workshop at World Geothermal conference 2026	Geothermal community (especially superhot geothermal); industry; early career researchers	<p>Half-day Workshop on Superhot Geothermal Energy;</p> <p>travel grants for ECRs to participate and engage; focus on industry</p>	2-5 June 2026
EPOS ERIC	ITS session at EGU26	International RIs in solid Earth sciences (AuScope, EarthScope and GNS-NZ)	<p>Showcase multi- and cross-disciplinary scientific use cases of global reach/interest;</p> <p>consolidate relations with the RIs; identify new scientific use cases for communication / dissemination purposes</p>	4 May 2026

Responsible partner(s)	Event	Involved Stakeholders	Objectives	Date
EPOS ERIC, CNRS	EPOS ON Summer School 2026	ECR and PhD students	Offer comprehensive training on RDM in solid Earth sciences, providing hands-on session to make the most of the EPOS Platform and learn how to use automated workflows in research work; engage with young researchers and foster their long-term involvement in the RI	28 June - 4 July, Olot, (Spain)
EPOS ERIC	EPOS Days 2027 and final EPOS ON event	Project Partners and Linked Third Parties, SCC, the TCS and ICS, ECR, International Partners, New communities	Present the project and its key activities and key exploitable results to the wider EPOS Community; Engage with new communities, international partners and ECR Conclude the EPOS ON project and plan for the future	June 2027, dates TBA

13. Appendix V – Participation to external events – Project period 2

The table below provides an overview of the events in which the project plans to participate during the second reporting period, based on information available at the time of writing. This should be considered a living resource, which will be regularly updated to reflect emerging opportunities and to ensure an optimal coverage of relevant dissemination and engagement channels.

It must be noted that participation to some of the events is opportunistic, since it is done in collaboration with other projects/organisations/initiatives so as to optimize the available resources in terms of funding/people/time while maximizing outcomes and synergies with related initiatives and projects, especially EC-Funded ones.

Event	Dates	Place	Envisaged participation
AGU - Earth, Space, and Environmental Global Data Resilience Convening	23 – 27 March 2026	Berlin	Participation in global discussion on data preservation/data loss mitigation
ENVRI Hackathon	13-15 April 2026	Rome	Interaction with the community
SUBMERSE final meeting	15-17 April 2026	Copenhagen	Participation/presentation; relevance: activity connected to new potential data/applications to be integrated.
“From Data to Hazard Modelling” Summer School	20-23 April 2026	Messina	Geo-INQUIRE workshop on seismic and tsunami hazards for Phd, PostDocs and ECR
EGU General Assembly 2026	03-08 May 2026	Vienna	Contributions on EPOS Open Source, Jupyter Notebooks, vocabulary harmonizations through AI; booth; training session; ITS session.
RIAGE workshop	18-19 May 2026	London	Presentation Relevance: potential links with industry (reinsurance in particular)
GEO Symposium	26-28 May 2026	Geneva	Session/participation. Relevance: collaboration/coordination with GEO; promotion of the EPOS platform (through ENVRI) as a possible technical solution to be adopted in GEO

Monographers 2026	1-5 June 2026	Budapest	Engagement with the community, Presentation, possibly training
EQUIP-G Annual meeting+Workshop	2-5 June 2026	Potsdam	Engagement with the community, Presentation
Final Annual meeting GEO-INQUIRE	16-18 June 2026	Potsdam	Engagement with the community, adoption of useful KERs (Key Exploitable Results)
CERIS Disaster Research Days	30 June-2 July 2026	Bruxelles	Presentation of WP3 KERs and promotion (demo/presentation)
EGI2026	21-25 September 2026	Ghent	Keynote speech
EOSC Symposium	14-16 October 2026	Florence	TBD*
ICRI	1-4 December 2026	Rome	TBD*
IUGG27	16-22 July 2027	Incheon, Republic of Korea	TBD*

*Programme not yet disclosed at the time of updating the document